

A Study of Impact of Anxiety on Academic Achievement of Graduate Females

Dr. Anjali Gupta

Associate Professor Institute of Teacher Education, Modinagar, Ghaziabad, U.P., India

Author Email: dranjali1972@gmail.com

Abstract—A person who has anxiety may not be able to devote his full energy in the performance of a task. It is, therefore, considered by many that anxiety interferes with the activity and so learning is impeded. A research study was under taken to study the impact of anxiety on academic achievement of female graduate of degree college. The sample was selected on the basis of random sampling. The standardized tool of Sinha's comprehensive anxiety test was used.

Academic achievement scores were collected from the annual exam records. The data obtained from the survey was analysed by using mean, SD and t-Test.

Keywords: Anxiety, Academic Achievement.

I. INTRODUCTION

Women are the key to nation's progress. The new Education Policy 1986, gave special emphasis to Women Education. The revolutionary change in the status of women has taken place. A hundred years ago, education of women was frowned upon in India, but now women's education has become very important. Now a women need not resign herself to her fate.

From the pre-vedic to the modern times, the position of women has oscillated for better or for worse several times. In the ancient times students lived with their teachers in gurukuls & ashrams & received higher education in particular subjects. But a woman's life was confined completely to the four walls. In vedic times or during the last stages to the Roman civilization women had the opportunity for full spiritual progress & intellectual development.

After vedic phase, female educational received great set back due to the deterioration of the religious status of women. However, girls in royal & aristocratic families received literacy education.

During the Mughal period Higher Education was imparted in Madarasas. The percentage of literacy among women went down very rapidly. The purdah system stood in the way of girls beyond a certain age being sent to schools. The door education was open only for the women of elite classes.

The introduction of a systematic higher education was the contribution of the British period. But the East India Company attached no importance to women's education. Women still occupied an inferior position in society and most of them seemed like 'dump driven cattle'.

William Adams pointed out that all educational institution were reserved for males & the entire female population was thrust into the darkness of ignorance. It is true that some enlightened women did participate in socio-political activities but women in general were out of the fray. Only a few girls managed to find a place in boy's schools, and even that with greatest difficulty. It was in the middle of the British Rule that certain sections of society the social reformers, philanthropists, government, voluntary organisations, social scientists & journalists became conscious of the status of women & made their contributions to the elevation of Indian womanhood. Glancing at the education of women 1857 to 1902, the India Education Commission declared that women's educational was in deplorably backward state and that is should be improved scientifically as much as possible.

In 1902, women's education assumed a form of a movement. In 1904 Mrs. Annie Besant set up a Hindi Girl's College at Benaras. In 1916 the first medical college exclusively for girls was set up at Delhi. In the same year the S.N.D.T Women's University was established at Bombay. Between 1917 & 1947, women's education grew rapidly.

After Independence, a number of acts and legislation have been passed, not only to protect-women from excesses but also to improve their standard of living. Now, there are facilities for higher education for women in every field of life and the number of women candidates in almost all examinations is increasing. In the modern world, women have to face many problems in day to today life. They are not merely looking after the house, rearing children but playing an important role outside the four walls of house. They are taking a new responsibilities & duties along with many problems which causes worry. Worry is an imaginary fear. It is referred by some psychologists as 'anxiety'. Anxiety is considered as a block to an activity. A person who suffers from anxiety may not be able to devoted his full energy in the performance of a task. It is therefore, considered by many that anxiety interferes with the activity and so learning is impeded.

II. RATIONALE OF THE STUDY

Anxiety is a common problem of us. It plays a critical role in our life. High level of anxiety interferes with concentration and memory, which are very critical for academic success. It is also true that without any anxiety, most of us would lack the motivation to study for exams, write in papers and do daily homework. A moderate amount of anxiety helps in academic

performance by creating motivation. But if your anxiety level is very low you may experience the same low level of academic performance similar to student having an excessively high anxiety level. A number of studies have been carried out to establish the various factors which directly or indirectly influence the academic achievement of the students. The present study was too undertaken to find out the possible influence of anxiety of female graduates on their academic achievement. Here in the present investigation the investigator put forward a step to analyse the relationship between the anxiety and its possible impact over academic achievement.

III. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

To find the anxiety level (General anxiety level) of graduate females.

To find out the impact of anxiety on the academic achievement of graduate females.

III.I. HYPOTHESIS

There is no significant difference in anxiety level of graduate females.

There is no impact of anxiety on the academic achievement of graduate females.

III.II. SAMPLE

The present study was conducted on female graduate students of female degree colleges. The sample were selected on the basis of random sampling.

III.III. TOOL OF THE STUDY

SINHA'S COMPREHENSIVE ANXIETY TEST

Comprehensive Anxiety Test (SCAT) Hindi/English. It contains 90 items of manifest anxiety. It is highly reliable and valid. Time 15 to 20 minutes. Scoring is simple. Level of anxiety may be classified in five categories.

III.IV. ADMINISTRATION OF TOOLS

The test were administered to the sampled female graduate students. The questionnaire were distributed to the sample and were collected after a few days. The marks of graduation were used as their academic achievement.

III.V. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

The data were collected from 100 graduate female students and scoring was done. On the basis of scores the graduate female students were categories under three anxiety level. They are: High anxiety level, Normal anxiety level, Low anxiety level.

The impact of anxiety on the academic achievement was studied of the graduate female students possessing low, normal and high anxiety level (each separately with their academic achievement).

To test the significance of mean difference (of anxiety scores and academic achievement marks), the t value was calculated and is presented in tabulated form.

Table 1: Significance of mean of difference of low anxiety score and academic achievement marks of graduate female students.

Category	Number	Mean	S.D.	Df	't'	LS
Academic Achievement marks	50	54.56	8.49	98	23.5	0.05
Low anxiety score	50	16	7.50			

t (tab) (refer to significant at 0.05 level with 98 df =1.98)

The score from Table-1 indicates significant difference between the academic achievement marks and anxiety score of graduate female students possessing low anxiety level because the calculated value of 't' is more than the tabulated value at 5% of significance for degree of freedom ($t = 1.98, p > 0.05$).

It shows that low anxiety has a positive impact on the academic achievement of graduate female students. The students who are generally low anxious are believed to be less motivated and less attentive but Table 1 shows that students who are low anxious are average achievers. The general anxiety does not impact on the academic achievement.

Table 2: Significance of mean difference of normal anxiety score and academic achievement marks of graduate female students.

Category	Number	Mean	S.D.	Df	't'	LS
Academic Achievement marks	45	55.71	5.17	88	8.55	0.05
Normal anxiety score	45	43.22	8.34			

t (tab) (refer to significant at 0.05 level with 88 df = 1.99)

The score from Table-2 indicated significant difference between the academic achievement marks and (general) anxiety score of graduate female students possessing normal anxiety level because the calculated value of 't' is more than the tabulated value at 5% level of significance for 88 degree of freedom ($t=1.99$, $P>0.05$).

Normal anxiety has a positive impact on the academic achievement of graduate female students. Students who possess normal anxiety level are believed to be good learners. Students possessing normal anxiety level are above average achievers. Normal anxiety helps the students to pay appropriate attention to studies also. They are generally anxious about learning also..

Table 3: Significance of mean difference of high anxiety score and academic achievement marks of graduate female students.

Category	Number	Mean	S.D.	Df	't'	LS
Academic Achievement marks	5	46.2	4.31	8	-6.89	0.05
High anxiety Score	5	67.42	5.37			

t (tab) (refer to significant at 0.05 level with 88 df = 1.99)

The score from Table-3 indicate that graduate female students having high anxiety level have a negative impact on the academic achievement as there is a significant difference between calculated and tabulated 't' value ($t=2.31$, $P < 0.05$).

Students who are generally high anxious have an adverse impact on their academic achievement.

IV. FINDINGS

On the basis of analysis and interpretation of data it has been observed that anxiety had relatively little impact on the academic achievement. The conclusion of the present investigation reveals that students of low anxiety and normal anxiety have a positive impact on academic achievement whereas the students suffering from high-anxiety are low achievers. Over-anxious students have difficulty in making progress in learning. They develop patterns of behaviour which are undesirable. They need counselling and psychotherapy.

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